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Citizens as lawmakers: legal innovation and the competing moralities of environmental juridification

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ABSTRACT

Law has increasingly become a relevant political language and a field of political contestation for citizens. In the context of socioenvironmental disputes, citizens have appealed to the courts or become involved in lawmaking as means of asserting their rights and worldviews. Such citizen engagements with law, I argue, amount to a form of worldmaking, as they allow for the introduction of situated moral values that challenge existing notions, rooted in liberal legality, about the environment, development, and sovereignty. This article explores this argument through the prism of the twelve-year long citizen opposition to mining in El Salvador and citizen engagement with law that culminated in the country's 2017 national ban on metal mining. It focuses on two processes of citizen-led legal experimentation: participation in a commercial arbitration dispute through two *amicus curiae* submissions and the production of several iterations of law drafts. The ethnographic research on which the article is based employed a networked methodology with a constellation of citizen actors whose engagements with law brought about the mining ban and articulated a set of alternative moral values.

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Introduction

On 29 March 2017, El Salvador's Legislative Assembly discussed and voted in a blanket ban on metallic mining that would become the first of its kind in the world. The ban passed with 69 votes out of 84, a share well above the simple majority of 42 required to introduce or reform laws through legislative decree in El Salvador. The ban was widely considered inevitable, to the point that no MP dared say anything negative during that day's legislative debate. Those who disagreed simply did not turn up for the vote. Thus did El Salvador become the first country in the world to ban all forms of artisanal and industrial metal mining.¹ Crucially, although codified by Salvadoran

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legislators, the ban was citizen-crafted. It resulted from a political-legal process spanning more than a decade in which citizen participants in various grassroots and civil society organisations and NGOs, as well as local populations in would-be mine areas, sought to assert their views about how the country's mineral deposits and water bodies should be governed. These Salvadoran citizens pursued various legal mechanisms, became knowledgeable about law, discussed and challenged aspects of it, and fostered legal innovations. In the process they put forth several drafts of a mining ban; the latest, produced largely by the country's religious sector with the participation of NGOs and civil society organisations, but modelled on previous citizen drafts, was the one discussed and passed by the Legislative Assembly in 2017.

Lawmaking is often assumed to be the preserve of legislatures, courtrooms, and the executive. My aim in this article is to explore how legal arenas are increasingly becoming the locus of environmental politics and how citizens involved in disputes over resource governance – specifically those who oppose resource extraction – participate in these arenas. Whether their participation manifests through law enforcement or lawmaking processes, these citizens thereby become re-constituted as 'legal subjects'. In other words, as citizens increasingly become plaintiffs or experts in law, their self-imaginings and identities are inevitably transformed, such that their political envisionings and participation are deeply coloured by the languages and possibilities afforded by law.² Moreover, through iterative engagements with law as rights-bearing individuals, citizens are reshaping categories of political subjects that are grounded in evolving notions of rights and justice.³

El Salvador is no exception in this regard; it is one among many countries in Latin America and beyond that raises questions about the legal practices in which citizens and other non-governmental actors engage to assert their rights over territory and natural materials and about the constructions of self and sociality that result from such practices.⁴ These citizens are crafting and transforming 'legal cultures', that is, the available repertoires of ever-changing ideational and behavioural aspects pertaining to law that are in turn constitutive of their own identities.⁵ Interestingly, as I will show in this article, legal cultures concerning the environment are offering possibilities, albeit limited, for the political expression of alternative moralities regarding nature, development, and sovereignty, thereby yielding distinct forms of juridification.

I draw in this article from ethnographic research and interviews conducted during fieldtrips to El Salvador between 2014 and 2018; from the analysis of legal documents collected during these fieldwork trips; and from online repositories.⁶ While doing research on the conflicts over mining in El Salvador, I observed a myriad of instances in which Euro-Western liberal law was the language in which disputes over natural materials or disparate visions of their governance were couched by a range of actors. This language emerged in various guises during my fieldwork on the divergent perspectives on mineral governance in El Salvador: in lawsuits filed by two international corporations via an investor-state dispute settlement mechanism; citizen attempts to redraft the laws that regulate extraction and produce legislative initiatives anew; the prominent role taken on by lawyers as well as the dissemination of legal knowledge and legal mechanisms among citizens; the filing of reports of extraction-related human rights violations through the Ombudsperson Office; and NGO-led public hearings at the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights. All these elements fall within 'legal formalism', that is,

the domain of officially sanctioned norms and institutions. Crucially, elements of legal formalism have increasingly been engaged by a variety of actors to pursue particular political outcomes, such as defining El Salvador's governance of mineral deposits. Many of these actors are citizens participating in grassroots movements and civil society organisations or working for NGOs.

I focus in this article on the participation of citizens in two instances of law engagement: a commercial arbitration procedure and a process of law drafting. To do so, I weave together legal submissions related to the arbitration proceedings, various citizen legislative initiatives aiming to regulate mining, and civil society accounts of these two processes. As the analysis of these legal documents and accounts illustrate, elements of legal formalism or those that replicate it have acquired wide currency and prevalence within the realm of environmental politics, with citizens seeking to appropriate or even transform them. Before exploring these two processes, I take a step back to revisit the existing scholarship on the proliferation of law and the legalisation of political disputes within sociolegal studies and the anthropology of law. I also adopt a historical perspective and suggest what may be specific to juridified disputes in which the environment is placed centre stage and how these disputes are unique to the Latin American region. Ultimately, building on scholarship addressing the embedment in territory of place-based populations and their onto-epistemologies, the article claims that counter-hegemonic uses of law involving natural materials and territories introduce alternative moralities that necessarily shape engagements with law. In doing so, these moralities have the potential, albeit limited, to transform Euro-Western liberal legality's objectification of territory as a 'resource', promoting instead an understanding of territory as a web of life and a mode of existence.

The juridification of environmental politics

The last quarter of the twentieth century and the beginning of the new millennium have seen an increasing recourse to courts and other judicial procedures for the settlement of controversies and disputes in a variety of life domains, including increasing judicial intervention in matters previously considered strictly political and outside the purview of the judiciary. Sociolegal scholars have described this process as the 'judicialization of politics'.⁷ While global in scale,⁸ this phenomenon has taken on particular significance throughout Latin America since the 1980s and has galvanised transdisciplinary debates within sociolegal studies about the role of law, courts, and law-like mechanisms.⁹ This phenomenon is not new: colonial Latin America was founded on law and law has remained central in the postcolony.¹⁰ Indigenous peoples in regions such as Mexico and the Andes engaged extensively with colonial legal institutions to settle disputes even as they maintained and interwove customary forms of law, resulting in diverse manifestations of legal pluralism throughout the colonial period and until the rise of European nation-states in the nineteenth century.¹¹ Crucially, at the end of the twentieth century, as Latin America democratised, constitutions emphasising rights proliferated and human rights discourses gained prominence. Legal institutions, languages, and instruments thus became ever more salient as a basis for rights-based citizenship and as a means of legitimising certain policies and governmental decisions in this region—

notwithstanding the many instances in which the rule of law remains inefficient or exclusionary.¹²

With the end of the Cold War, the transnational legal and moral language of human rights, and its mechanisms and procedures, assumed a prominence they had not enjoyed before. In the latter third of the twentieth century, the convergence of various political, social and economic transformations – including a rise in neoliberal policies and consequent roll back of the state, the falling off of nationalism and national polities as a by-product of increasing global connectedness, and the emergence of identity-based transnational communities – contributed to the proliferation of human rights rhetoric.¹³ From the early 1990s onwards, human rights became the global language for claims for political and social transformation and understandings of personhood, that is, ‘a global moral lingua franca’.¹⁴ The language of human rights dissolved irreducible cultural differences into the aggregate of the moral person as the subject of rights, thereby serving as a means of commensuration.¹⁵ In Latin America, the language of human rights was disseminated by Western NGOs, many of them involved in development practices. Human rights were adopted in the region not simply as a legal strategy but ‘as a new form of self-regard, a new form of being in the world, one that was anchored in a radical theory of human equality’.¹⁶ This is partly explained because human rights in Latin America took root over a historical foundation that wed emancipatory ideologies and commoning values rooted in Catholic morality – a combination which yielded idiosyncratic forms of citizenship that have pursued both individual rights and collective social justice.¹⁷

The global dimension of the language of human rights has thus enabled law to travel across scales (temporal, jurisdictional) and geographies.¹⁸ Indeed, the invocation and mobilisation of human rights has occurred at the interface of a plurality of legal orders – a phenomenon called ‘interlegality’.¹⁹ Local, subnational, national, regional, and international norms, mechanisms and institutions overlap and co-exist, whether harmoniously or in competition. In addition, many indigenous peoples continue to embrace their own forms of law and legal rationality which they mobilise at the interface of hegemonic forms of law, and some countries in the region have recognised indigenous law jurisdictions.²⁰ In this vein, notions of rights are fed by and feed back into a plurality of normative understandings and jurisdictions. The result is the vernacularisation of human rights, with actors at different scales adopting and elaborating locally situated expressions of global norms.²¹ Such situated forms of human rights law interpretation, implementation and making may be also shaped by the alternative indigenous onto-epistemologies that are often in play, giving way to a ‘legal pluralism as pluriverse’ or a diversity of ‘onto-legalities’.²² In other words, different ontological notions and enactments of reality may engender diverse forms of law.²³

As the rhetoric of rights and law more generally have expanded to ever more life domains, the term ‘judicialisation’ has fallen short as a means of addressing these processes. Indeed, as O’Donnell has pointed out, the judicialisation of politics is only one aspect of contemporary Latin America’s broader processes of judicialisation and the juridification of social relations, that is, the increasingly broad currency that repertoires of legal languages, mechanisms and practices enjoy beyond the courts and formalist legal arenas.²⁴ Some earlier socio-legal scholars, Habermas among them, have already employed the term juridification to refer to the proliferation of law and its expansion

to ever more social spheres, with profound consequences for the latter, which see freedoms legally guaranteed by the state yet constrained by increased regulation.²⁵ The term ‘juridification’ has thus been coined to denote a ‘colonisation of the lifeworld’ and an ‘increased ‘density’ of law’, in Habermas’s terms;²⁶ that is, ‘the growing legalization of social, political, and economic life’.²⁷ From Habermas’s perspective, there is a depoliticising and distorting operation involved in juridification, as law imposes an abstraction, standardisation, and commensuration of social phenomena that undermines their very essence.²⁸ He further asserts that juridification entails a ‘technocratic consciousness’ and ‘a repression of ethics as a category of life’.²⁹

Yet this unprecedented proliferation of law encompasses an even wider range of processes than acknowledged by Habermas, from its expansion to social domains not previously regulated by law to an increasing settlement of disputes through law, the expansion of judicial power or the legal framing of worldviews.³⁰ Not only do these processes lead to the emergence and development of ‘legal cultures’³¹ characterised by the mobilisation of existing law within the courts and judicature, but they also foster new normative understandings and emerging rights. Additionally, they shape the political subjectivities of actors without legal training who mobilise law in what constitutes an ‘iterative process’ – a process that counterbalances the structuring qualities of law and its constitutive role of personhood with citizens’ ability to mould law through iterative engagements with it.³² In the juridification processes that are the focus of this article, in which law is mobilised and articulated by citizens to settle disputes or address conflicts, and grievances are legally framed, law becomes the language of ‘aspirational politics’³³ and juridification is far from being depoliticising or devoid of ethics. Additionally, juridification processes around a particular source of conflict entail ‘the mobilisation of different legal orders’ – from international human rights law to civil and criminal law or forms of indigenous law – and the movement between them.³⁴

Political disputes and rights-based claims have thus increasingly taken on a legal form. Grassroots, NGOs, and citizens worldwide have played a leading role in generating ‘embryonic legal alternatives’ to counter legal orthodoxies that exclude and marginalise them or their worldviews and ways of living.³⁵ This ‘legal mobilization from below’, which may occur in the interstices between the legal/illegal/extra-legal and across scales, articulates political claims with legal languages.³⁶ As I demonstrate in this article, this mobilisation of legal expert knowledge can engage existing norms to imbue them with different moral values and ontological perspectives or can transform and rewrite law to align it with said values and perspectives. These processes of legal experimentation and legal innovation, which are the focus of my research, point to the emergence of prominent forms of ‘legal citizenship’. By mobilising law and legal knowledge, I argue, actors’ relationship to the body politic, as they conceive and enact it, is transformed. They emerge as legal personas who do not just regard themselves as entitled to rights but who learn the expert languages, knowledge, and mechanisms to claim these rights, practise them and, in some cases, creatively transform them.

The proliferation of citizen-led rights-based claims or rights-talk is not unique to Latin America, nor does it lack precedents. A seminal instance was the 1960s Civil Rights Movement in the United States which engaged law in different ways, from aiming to reform laws and pursuing litigation to attempting to expand civil rights and infuse them with new meanings.³⁷ In Latin America, citizen-led mobilisation of law has been

prominent with regard to issues such as reproductive and gender identity rights, or transitional justice-related grievances and claims for redress.³⁸ Nonetheless, the citizen mobilisation of law to claim rights relating to the environment has specific traits. According to Boyd, during the last quarter of the twentieth century an ‘environmental rights revolution’ took root, underpinned by a coalescence of democratisation processes, an expansion of constitutional rights, and a rise of an environmental consciousness.³⁹ This revolution reached the courts as well as myriad other legal and quasi-legal or legal-like arenas. While all juridified claims or rights-based disputes are grounded in moral values, the specificity that inheres in environmental disputes is worth exploring if we are to find pathways for addressing the urgency and dramatic nature of the unfolding climate crisis.

Citizen-led environmental juridification entails acting upon understandings of territory and environment that may radically differ. For populations for whom territory is integral to their way of living, relationships to ‘nature’ – even if they include extraction – are conceived and valued in unique terms. Nature and territory are not regarded merely, if at all, as ‘resources’ available for human exploitation; they are the web of life of which humans are a part. Extractive practices that are not respectful of the intimate entanglements between humans and nonhumans and the territory they inhabit are thus conceived as destructive not just of earth life and livelihoods but also of modes of existence and even alternative worlds.⁴⁰ These conceptions of ‘radical relationality’⁴¹ are emerging in extraction-related conflicts throughout Latin America that involve indigenous populations who conceive of nonhumans as agentive or sentient beings.⁴² The emergence of indigenous populations as vocal political actors in recent decades has illuminated the different ontologies at play vis-à-vis nature, the environment and extraction. In presenting nonhumans or earth-beings – such as mountains, water, and soil – as sentient beings, indigenous peoples in Peru, Bolivia, Ecuador or Chile do indeed make political interventions, even if these exceed or disturb our understandings of politics as usual.⁴³

In the case of El Salvador, it would be an overstatement to suggest that different ontologies are in play. The existence of ethnic identities is disputed, and they have not been mobilised to the extent that they have in other Latin American territories. Yet, as I will show in subsequent sections, other moralities have prevailed in the legal cultures taking root in El Salvador’s environmental politics – moralities that challenge and unsettle the contours and the foundations upon which aspects of development, and in this case legality as well, have been premised. While El Salvador’s legal cultures do not transpire a different reality upon which meaning is created, as de la Cadena and other scholars suggest is the case for the agitations fostered by alternative onto-epistemologies, they do nonetheless introduce alternative forms of worlding or configuring the world otherwise. This article thus demonstrates that even peasant, non-indigenous populations are articulating worldviews and political-legal arguments that, underpinned by different moralities regarding nature and territory and by nuanced notions of radical relationality, counter extractive practices undertaken without their consent and oblivious of their desires, forms of worlding, and histories. These alternative moralities are partly shaped by international development and environmental NGOs such as Oxfam, Caritas, Justice, Peace and Integrity of Creation (JPIC), Heinrich Böll Foundation or Friends of the Earth, as their funding and support is inflected with particular understandings of politics and ecology.

Research on the mobilisation of law requires what I have conceptualised as ‘networked methodologies’, that is, methodologies that enable tracing and mapping out the constellations of actors and legal artefacts and ideas that are bound together through multi- and trans-scalar juridification processes to account for ‘law’s travels’.⁴⁴ This kind of methodology is ‘multi-sited’⁴⁵ and ‘deterritorialised’⁴⁶; it is based on ethnographic research that is not premised on geographic locality but makes the aforementioned constellation the site of fieldwork. It is thus based on a distinct understanding of locality altogether which differs from traditional ethnographic research whereby ‘the field’ has been constitutive of the anthropological method and discipline⁴⁷; the ethnography of juridification is no longer a topological methodology. Such ‘un-sited fieldwork’ no longer collapses space, place and field or pursues the holism that underlies multi-sited fieldwork as initially conceived.⁴⁸ While I have visited the areas where the disputed mines are located to get a feel for them and understand the place-based moralities in play, these areas are not as central to the research. Instead, it is the networks of local populations, human rights lawyers, NGOs, international organisations, ombudsperson offices, courts and other institutions that mobilise law that are; and so are their generation and mobilisation of legal instruments and artefacts in the process. Due to the extension of juridification processes over time and the resulting changes in the constellations of actors and legal artefacts involved as well as the meanings and conceptions of evolving environments, this kind of networked methodology is not just deterritorialised but also longitudinal. It requires fieldwork conducted over extended periods of time that can capture ‘the long arc of juridification’.⁴⁹ What follows is an analysis of two forms of legal mobilisation based on this form of networked research.

Investor v. state arbitration

The first form of citizen-led legal engagement that I explore in this article relates to an arbitration procedure involving an international private investor (a Canadian-owned mining company) and El Salvador’s government. Commercial arbitration is a quasi-judicial mechanism devised to settle disputes between international private investors and host states through binding adjudication or conciliation. It is most often initiated by the former when host states have allegedly breached contractual agreements, failed to offer fair and equitable treatment, or incurred expropriation.⁵⁰ As such, this kind of mechanism excludes the participation of citizens or other third parties who consider themselves directly affected by the outcome while providing a legal infrastructure that protects international investment flows.⁵¹ In the arbitration case I describe below, however, Salvadoran grassroots and NGOs, with the support of an international human rights organisation, got involved in the process through two *amicus curiae*. Although this participation was the subject of controversy, to some it represented an opportunity to introduce their arguments for why the company’s claims were baseless and its extractive activities illegitimate. These arguments were expressed in the form of moral perspectives which, as argued in the previous section, are rooted in territory, interactions with the environment, and specific histories.

The *Pac Rim Cayman LLC v. Republic of El Salvador* arbitration procedure I describe herein extended over seven years (ICSID Case No. ARB/09/12).⁵² On 9 December 2008, the international law firm Crowell & Moring, representing Pac Rim Cayman LLC⁵³

(hereinafter Pac Rim), a shell subsidiary of Pacific Rim Corp., sent El Salvador's ambassador to the United States (US) a Notice of Intent to Submit a Claim to Arbitration against El Salvador in accordance with the Dominican Republic-Central America Free Trade Agreement (DR-CAFTA) with the US and the Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes Between States and Nationals of Other States.⁵⁴ This Notice of Intent explained on what grounds Pac Rim found El Salvador had acted in an 'arbitrary' and 'unlawful' manner. Pac Rim argued that over a four-year period El Salvador's Ministry of Economy (MINEC) and Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (MARN) – the two authorities that ruled mining operations in the country – had neglected to respond to the company's application for an exploitation concession in spite of its considerable investments in exploration in the country and its compliance with Salvadoran and international law. On 30 April 2009, Pac Rim filed the actual Notice of Arbitration under the auspices of the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID), the World Bank institution that conducts private investor v. state conciliation and arbitration.⁵⁵

This Notice of Arbitration initiated the seven-year long legal procedure that resulted in the ICSID award delivered in 2016 in favour of the Salvadoran state. The dispute was relegated to the offices of legal firms and the ICSID arbitrating tribunal. Subjecting the dispute to this quasi-legal procedure privileged the question of whether the Salvadoran government had behaved lawfully, per corporate-friendly legislation and agreements, over a consideration of the Salvadoran government's right to reassess its natural resource governance policy and the appropriateness of extraction in the country. Indeed, as discussed above, ICSID originated in the search for guarantees for investors, and critics have pointed out that it undermines host states' ability to effect policy change in line with transformations and obligations in human rights and environmental international law.⁵⁶ Since this institution's ethos is underpinned by the World Bank tenet that foreign direct investment is a crucial driver of development in emerging economies considered to have inadequate regulations and weak judicial sectors, ICSID works as a guarantor that host states will abide by established bilateral or multilateral trade and investment agreements and thereby respect contracts with investors.⁵⁷

Pac Rim's investment in the El Dorado mining project, located in El Salvador's northern Cabañas Department, and its application for an exploitation concession was encouraged by an investor-friendly environment fostered since the 1990s by successive pro-business governments led by the conservative Republican Nationalist Alliance (ARENA). Advised by the US-funded think tank Salvadoran Foundation for Economic and Social Development (FUSADES) and lender organisations like the World Bank, the ARENA governments ushered in legislation that would transform El Salvador from an agro-export economy to one based on financial services and foreign direct investment, especially in labour-intensive manufacturing.⁵⁸ Following a process akin to that of other Latin American countries, the Salvadoran governments gradually endorsed Washington Consensus pro-market regulation and policies which paved the way for economic liberalisation and the protection of foreign direct investment.⁵⁹

Worldwide regulatory harmonisation promoting investment in the mining sector was achieved via, for instance, the conditional loans of institutions such as the World Bank.⁶⁰ In line with these legal reforms, a new Mining Law was passed in El Salvador in 1996 that replaced its prior 1922 Mining Code.⁶¹ The country's Legislative Assembly justified this

law update by invoking the need to ‘harmonise it with the principles of a social market economy that is convenient for investors in the mining sector’.⁶² To further incentivise mining ventures, in 2001 the law was reformed to, among other things, extend the duration of the exploration licenses from 5 to 8 years and lower royalties from 3 to a maximum of 2 percent of each trimester’s net sales of the extracted mineral calculated as per international market prices. Other developments that concerned the regulation of this sector and attributed substantive rights to private investors were the 1999 Investment Law and the 2004 ratification of the DR-CAFTA trade agreement with the United States. Both these instruments included provisions that acknowledged the jurisdiction of the ICSID. This legal scenario was conducive to foreign direct investment in El Salvador’s mining sector from international companies coinciding with the mid-1990s mineral boom.

However, in 2006 the Salvadoran government changed course and established a *de facto* moratorium on all mineral-related concessions that would remain in place until the ban was passed in 2017.⁶³ Strikingly enough, it was a government led by the investor-friendly ARENA party that had initially promoted the mining law that enacted this moratorium. The moratorium was not actively expressed in the form of policy or legislation (what would have constituted a *de jure* moratorium); rather, it was implicit in the fact that the government never granted Pac Rim an exploitation concession or, for that matter, any exploration licenses to any other companies from 2006. In March 2004, Pac Rim had requested the environmental permit that the 1996 Mining Law stipulates is a prerequisite for obtaining an exploitation concession. From then through December 2006, El Salvador’s Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (MARN) requested amendments from Pac Rim of the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) the company had submitted.

Pac Rim claimed that although it had replied to all the requests it received through December 2006, the MARN abruptly ‘ceased all official communication with the company and thereby failed to finalise the company’s application for an environmental permit that would have in turn allowed it to complete the exploitation concession submitted in December 2004’.⁶⁴ The Pac Rim complaint continues: ‘Nor did the company ever receive a response to the application for exploration in the areas of Huacuco, Pueblos and Guaco submitted by one of its subsidiaries in September 2005’.⁶⁵ The Salvadoran government’s legal defendant, in turn, claimed all throughout the ICSID proceedings that Pac Rim never satisfied the requirements of Salvadoran law, including those pertaining to the environmental permit. The ICSID award would eventually corroborate El Salvador’s state claims.

The *de facto* moratorium was announced to all mining companies operating in El Salvador in May 2007 and publicly confirmed in March 2008, when President Elías Antonio Saca declared his unwillingness to grant mining concessions.⁶⁶ The shift in ARENA’s mineral governance policy seems to have been motivated partly by concern over its increasing loss of hegemony. Since the 2003 legislative election, ARENA’s declining share of the vote had negatively correlated with the leftwing Farabundo Martí National Liberation Front (FMLN)’s share, and 2008 polls predicted the likelihood of an FMLN victory in the 2009 presidential elections. In a context of mounting public opposition to mining from even such broadly influential institutions as the country’s Catholic Bishops Conference,⁶⁷ ARENA refrained from delivering a positive response to Pac Rim’s application for an exploitation concession and publicly proclaimed the *de facto* moratorium during the run-up to the March 2009 presidential elections. In view of

the ARENA leader's public statement and the victory in the 2009 elections of the FMLN, which had publicly endorsed the *de facto* moratorium during the electoral campaign, Pac Rim took the step of suing the Salvadoran state as announced a few months earlier through its December 2008 Notice of Intent, referenced at the beginning of this section.

In the Notice of Intent, the company claimed that El Salvador had breached both DR-CAFTA and its own domestic law in various ways. According to Pac Rim, by not granting the relevant permits that the 1996 Mining Law allows, subject to compliance with the law's requirements, and by ceasing communication with the company, the Salvadoran government had not respected domestic law. As for El Salvador's alleged transgression of DR-CAFTA's provision 10.5, Pac Rim argued that the Salvadoran government failed to treat the company's investments in the same manner as those of other environmentally risky sectors in which the government had continued to approve exploitation concessions. The company contended: 'El Salvador's unjustified conduct with respect to the Enterprises' [Pacific Rim subsidiaries in El Salvador] concession and permit applications has rendered the Enterprises worthless, and thus constitutes a direct and indirect expropriation of PRC's [Pacific Rim Cayman] investments in El Salvador. Pursuant to DR-CAFTA, international law, and Salvadoran legislation, such an uncompensated taking is unlawful'.⁶⁸ Pac Rim requested compensation for its loss in various ways, including US \$75⁶⁹ million to cover the investment costs incurred in exploration activities and an additional sum (to be established by the ICSID) to compensate the company for its loss of revenue due to what Pac Rim considered a *de facto* expropriation of its investment.⁷⁰

Pac Rim's legal battle via the ICSID obliged the FMLN government led by Mauricio Funes, which had defeated ARENA in the 2009 elections and taken office in June 2009, to seek legal support from Dewey & LeBoeuf, a Washington-based private law firm. A member of MINEC's Department of Hydrocarbons and Mines explained in an interview that El Salvador's Prosecutor Office lacked the experience to defend El Salvador in the ICSID arbitration procedure, thus necessitating that a substantial amount of the public budget be devoted to legal representation.⁷¹ Indeed, law firms specialising in international commercial arbitration have proliferated as the number of cases against states filed through ICSID and other such arbitration mechanisms has risen. Senior Counsel Luis Parada – a Salvadoran lawyer with extensive experience in investor-state arbitration who initially worked for Dewey & LeBoeuf and then, from 2012, for Foley Hoag⁷² – led El Salvador's legal defense, which rested on two basic claims: first, that Pac Rim was not granted the exploitation concession because it failed to satisfy the requirements of Salvadoran law;⁷³ and second, that the exploration license received by the company did not – contrary to what Pac Rim argued – automatically entitle the company to an exploitation concession.⁷⁴ El Salvador provided evidence of communication with the company to corroborate these claims. As I describe in the next section, while the ICSID oversees private investor v. state arbitration, Salvadoran citizens opposed to mining in El Salvador nonetheless became involved in the ICSID proceedings.

Imbuing arbitration with alternative moralities

Exploration started around San Isidro, the municipality nearest to the Pac Rim-owned El Dorado mining project, in 2004. Residents were then unaware of the repercussions of

mining but concerned that ‘white people’ were taking away rock samples from their land properties without permission. This led locals to ask themselves, ‘Do we support these projects or should we obtain more information about them?’ – as recalled by Ely, a member of the local development organisation Asociación de Desarrollo Económico y Social (Economic and Social Development Association, ADES).⁷⁵ Research by ADES and other local organisations soon raised alarming prospects about the impacts of mining on the land and water – especially given Cabañas’s dependence on small-scale agriculture – that in turn sparked opposition to the El Dorado project. The success of local mobilisation against the mine was rooted partly in a regional history of communal and political organising in both Cabañas and Chalatenango that has continued after the country’s civil war (1980–1992) through the local NGO ADES and the regional NGO Asociación para el Desarrollo de El Salvador (Association for the Development of El Salvador, CRIPDES). Both of these organisations developed out of efforts to repopulate areas of northern El Salvador with war refugees from the late 1980s, and they have remained relentless supporters of the FMLN in the postwar era.⁷⁶

ADES and CRIPDES coalesced with national NGOs and civil society organisations in the Mesa Nacional frente a la Minería Metálica (National Roundtable on Metallic Mining; henceforth Mesa Nacional). Founded in 2005, Mesa Nacional represented the consolidation of a pre-existing alliance of grassroots organisations, NGOs, and mobilised citizens from the northern departments of Cabañas and Chalatenango where would-be mines were located, national human rights NGOs, research institutes, and faith-based groups that opposed Pac Rim operations at El Dorado.⁷⁷ The coalition was partly facilitated by the early 2000s anti-CAFTA-DR mobilisation in El Salvador, which brought together myriad organisations opposed to neoliberalisation, and developed international alliances that contributed to the notoriety achieved by the case and the ensuing events thereof.⁷⁸ Through that mobilisation, El Salvador’s grassroots and civil society organisations and NGOs became part of a transnational constellation of actors through which ideas underpinning environmental agendas were shared.

For over a decade, Mesa Nacional members developed manifold strategies to publicly expose mining-related risks to the environment and the health of nearby residents and to promote a definitive ban on mining. In doing so, they received support from El Salvador’s Human Rights Ombudsperson Office as well as international human rights NGOs such as Oxfam America, Institute for Policy Studies, Friends of the Earth or the Centre for International Environmental Law (CIEL).⁷⁹ Significantly, along with repertoires of contention such as street actions, Mesa Nacional members resorted to legal and legal-like mechanisms to advance their goals.⁸⁰ Yet their embracement of these mechanisms did not necessarily mean that they considered the legal domain in and of itself rewarding or the solution to their predicaments. Their non-committal attitude towards the legal domain became evident in their involvement in the ICSID legal case via two *amicus curiae* submitted at different stages of the arbitral proceedings. The ‘*amicus curiae*’, which means literally ‘friend of the court’, is a juridical mechanism that allows a non-disputing party to present information that might bring a new perspective to a legal case and thereby assist the corresponding tribunal.

Various interviews with Mesa Nacional members revealed that the coalition’s decision to take part in the ICSID proceedings via two *amicus curiae* had been far from unanimous and was only taken forward by a handful of member organisations. ‘There was

debate among Mesa Nacional members', Claudio, a member of the coalition, explained. 'There were people who thought that submitting an *amicus curiae* entailed playing the game – legitimising the ICSID system. [...] Brazil is not an ICSID member and that does not affect its foreign direct investment. Bolivia, Ecuador, and Venezuela have already abandoned ICSID. So some thought that El Salvador should directly stop acknowledging ICSID'.⁸¹ For some Mesa Nacional members, in other words, taking part in the ICSID proceedings and following ICSID rules would only serve to lend credibility to a mechanism that they considered largely exclusionary given that it acknowledges arbitration solely between private investors and states and prioritises a notion of development they do not share – one which has economic growth based on extraction and private investment, rather than the wellbeing of citizens and the environments they inhabit, at its very centre.

On 20 May 2011, pursuant to the ICSID Arbitration Rules (Art. 37.2) that allow for non-disputing party intervention, a portion of Mesa Nacional filed its first *amicus curiae* to the ICSID tribunal arbitrating the case.⁸² With legal assistance from the Washington- and Geneva-based human rights organisation Center for International Environmental Law (CIEL), the subscribing organisations requested that ICSID dismiss Pac Rim's claim during the jurisdictional stage. They argued among other things that there were no grounds for Pac Rim's claim given that what was at stake was not a 'legal dispute' but a 'political' one. In their own words, 'El Salvador's public policy has begun to turn against metals mining, in recognition and reflection of the deeply destructive environmental and social effects that metals mining can pose to local communities. In short, this is clearly a political dispute',⁸³ by contrast to one of procedure and breach of law. The denial here of the legal nature of the dispute is noteworthy. It was a way for the member organisations of Mesa Nacional acting as *amici* to expose Pac Rim's way of proceeding as an attempt to judicialise and portray as lawbreaking what they instead regarded as a matter of Salvadorans' sovereignty to determine and implement public policy.

Member organisations of Mesa Nacional subscribing the *amicus curiae* also alleged that Pac Rim had engaged in an abuse of process in two ways: first, by changing the company's nationality from the Cayman Islands to the US right before filing the claim so as to benefit from DR-CAFTA arbitration and, second and more important for the purposes of this article, by taking what was actually a dispute between the company and the communities adjacent to El Dorado to a venue like ICSID in which Mesa Nacional (as the representative of the interests of these communities) could not participate, aside from the limited intervention of the *amicus curiae*. This point is particularly important for understanding how Mesa Nacional members have manifestly considered certain domains of law deeply exclusionary. In their 2011 *amicus curiae* they contended that 'Pac Rim's attempt to take a dispute centered between it and the affected communities to a forum where the communities have only limited discretionary rights is abusive in nature' as the communities 'have no right to appear [in order] to defend their position, but rather appear pursuant to this Tribunal's good graces by way of this limited *amicus curiae* submission'.⁸⁴

Although in June 2012 the ICSID tribunal rejected Pac Rim's claims based on DR-CAFTA because it was merely a shell company with no substantial business activities in the US and owned by a Canadian company, with Canada not being a signatory to

DR-CAFTA, it did admit the claims pertaining to El Salvador's 1999 Investment Law. At this stage of the proceedings, again with CIEL's support, a portion of Mesa Nacional member organisations submitted a second *amicus curiae* in July 2014, prior to the merits hearing that was to take place in September 2014.⁸⁵ This *amicus curiae* requested that Pac Rim's claims be dismissed given that the Salvadoran government had acted lawfully as per international human rights and environmental law. El Salvador's denial of Pac Rim's environmental permit due to the enforcement of national environmental regulation, Mesa Nacional argued, was in consonance with recent developments in international law that 'reflect the moral conscience regarding the inter-relationship between humanity and nature'.⁸⁶ In foregrounding the mutual relationship between human and environmental rights, Mesa Nacional built upon a worldview that posits a radical relationality between humanity and nature.⁸⁷

In its effort to justify Mesa Nacional's actions and claims via international law, the *amicus curiae* also argued that international environmental legislation, specifically Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration, acknowledges the public's right to participate through social dialogue in matters that concern the environment as well as its right to prescribe limits to any state's sovereignty over natural resources.⁸⁸ This was an attempt to expand the notion of sovereignty introduced in the first *amicus curiae*, noting that not only does El Salvador's sovereignty extend to social and environmental policy decision-making, but that Salvadoran citizens have a role to play in the public discussion of the policies. Finally, the *amicus curiae* underlined that Pac Rim's manoeuvres in Cabañas had fuelled local social conflicts.⁸⁹ In a country where wartime divisions have not yet been fully addressed or overcome, postwar homicide rates have been among the world's highest and political life has been permeated by various forms of violence⁹⁰, Pac Rim's actions in Cabañas were exacerbating political polarisation and sparking physical violence against anti-mining activists. Indeed, social unrest climaxed in 2009 with the assassination of three anti-mining activists and death threats received by many others.

In their first *amicus curiae*, the Mesa Nacional members involved expressed their view that Pac Rim's claim through ICSID was a means of disregarding the very organic nature of opposition to mining in El Salvador. Some Mesa Nacional members engaged in the two *amicus curiae* in order to exhaust all the possibilities and instruments available to them for the introduction of other moral values and perspectives on the dispute. In highlighting the political nature of the dispute, they affirmed the sovereignty of both the Salvadoran state and its citizenry to shape national development policy. They foregrounded the interdependency of human and environmental wellbeing and the consequent pre-eminence that both human and environmental rights must have in the delineation of national sustainable development agendas. As I will show next, Mesa Nacional members' engagement of law did not only surface through the ICSID arbitration proceedings but also in the form of lawmaking efforts that enabled a greater degree of innovation and experimentation, as in the drafting of legislative initiatives that laid out their own visions for the governance of Salvadoran territory and environment.

Lawmaking as moral practice

The involvement of Mesa Nacional members in law drafting is the second form of juridification that I explore in this article. It is a telling example of how citizens act out

legal subjectivities through juridification processes as they become ‘lawmakers’. In the mid-2000s, as opposition to mining gained momentum and led organisations of various persuasions to coalesce in Mesa Nacional, its members began discussing the possibility that mining be prohibited via legislation so as to consolidate the *de facto* moratorium.

From 2006 we said, well, it is worth prohibiting mining via a law because current legislation allows and encourages mining. [...] very quickly, we drafted a proposal and presented it to the Legislative Assembly, [hoping that] the central result would be the definitive prohibition of mining. We presented it in 2006 but there it remained; there was never a discussion of it. Well, during electoral campaigns we did some lobbying with the candidates. Especially in [the] 2009 [presidential elections] we thought as a movement that we should obtain a solid commitment; at least that the candidates of all parties sign a letter where they committed themselves to a prohibition of mining. Tony Saca said he would, but his term of office was concluding [...]. We managed to obtain a commitment from Funes. Funes signed a letter committing publicly to prohibiting mining during his term.

This is how, in an interview with me, ADES member Elsy⁹¹ described Mesa Nacional members’ first concerted attempt to engage with legal arenas. As an ADES representative of Mesa Nacional, Elsy is one of the coalition’s most vocal and visible members and for a long while the only female Mesa Nacional leader.

As relayed by Elsy, a first 72-provision legislation draft was handed over to El Salvador’s Legislative Assembly in 2006. This transpired almost two years after Pac Rim had submitted the application for an environmental permit that was a prerequisite for an exploitation concession and that the MARN had continually returned to the company with substantial remarks. With this legislation draft, entitled Law for the Regulation of Mining Activity in the Country (*Ley de regulación de la actividad minera en el país*), Mesa Nacional sought to replace the existing 1996 Mining Law and pursue the reform of non-metallic mineral extraction and the permanent prohibition of exploration and exploitation of metallic minerals, so as to firm up the ongoing moratorium no matter what political party came into office in the future.⁹² This draft, Mesa Nacional members surmised, would also serve to enshrine and lend legitimacy to their claims that mining projects in areas of Guatemala and Honduras that border, and therefore impact, El Salvador should likewise be shut down.⁹³ Yet, as mentioned by Elsy, this legislation proposal was never discussed by El Salvador’s Legislative Assembly despite repeated attempts to present it to deputies.⁹⁴ Nor were a 2007 legislative initiative submitted by then-PCN deputy Orlando Arévalo that reflected Pac Rim’s interests or one submitted in 2009 by the FMLN. Both of these drafts, contrary to Mesa Nacional efforts, aimed merely to reform the country’s mining activity.

In 2012, three years after the ICSID case had begun, the FMLN drafted a legislation proposal based on a Strategic Environmental Assessment of the mining sector that the government had commissioned from the Spanish firm TAU Consultores. This firm’s assessment underlined the risks of mining in El Salvador under the current legal, institutional, environmental, and social conditions and indicated that a ban on mining seemed a prudent step, at least until these conditions were reversed. The FMLN’s proposal, entitled the Special Law for the Suspension of Mining-Related Administrative Procedures (*Ley especial para la suspensión de procedimientos administrativos relativos a la minería*), would consolidate the moratorium on mining concessions indefinitely.

Yet the proposal was never discussed by the Legislative Assembly and was met with strong opposition from Mesa Nacional, which felt that a ‘suspension’ instead of a ‘ban’ left open the possibility of mining in the future under a government less concerned about the impacts of extraction.

On continuing her narration of Mesa Nacional’s involvement in lawmaking, Elsy recalled: ‘[...] last year (referring to 2013) we streamlined the legislation draft that we had presented in 2006, which had not even been discussed. [...] we felt it was very lengthy and decided to simplify it to five articles.’⁹⁵ The new proposal, entitled Special Law for Banning Metallic Mining in El Salvador (*Ley Especial de Prohibición de la Minería Metálica en El Salvador*), was presented to the Environmental and Climate Change Commission of the Legislative Assembly on 1 October after a rally that demonstrated nationwide public support for a mining ban.⁹⁶ This effort was likewise to no avail. In the light of the Legislative Assembly’s inaction vis-à-vis mining and in anticipation of the possibility of a negative ICSID ruling, on 28 May 2015 Mesa Nacional members took out a full-page advertisement in the leading Salvadoran broadsheet *La Prensa Gráfica*.⁹⁷ The advertisement appealed to the FMLN government of Salvador Sánchez Cerén to at least pass an executive decree consolidating the moratorium on mining, thereby circumventing the Legislative Assembly until this entity was open to discussing a permanent ban – a step never taken by the FMLN-led government.

El Salvador does not acknowledge citizen legislative initiatives as a mechanism that guarantees direct democracy.⁹⁸ Yet this lack has not prevented citizens from emulating the mechanism, drafting legislative initiatives, and lobbying incumbent deputies to submit these initiatives for consideration by the Legislative Assembly and its Commission on Environment and Climate Change. As a human rights organisation of lawyers that is part of Mesa Nacional, the Foundation for the Study of the Application of the Law (FESPAD) facilitated Mesa Nacional’s engagements with the law by dispensing legal advice and supplying the technical jargon and aesthetics that typify legislative initiatives. Other Mesa Nacional members, while not officially trained in law, participated in the drafting of the legislative initiative, debating its substance and drafts of the initiative once they had been generated by FESPAD with inputs from member organisations and citizens participating in workshops who, in the process, became self-educated in matters of law. This is the case of Mesa Nacional representatives like Elsy, who learned about law through their participation in the coalition. Members of Mesa Nacional regarded the various iterations of the legislative initiative as a collective endeavour by all those who had provided arguments and content for it. After a law was passed in 2017, Mesa Nacional played a fundamental role in disseminating it and promoting citizen embracement of it, by for instance creating a graphic pocket booklet including the text of the law, which they have used in workshops and training sessions in rural areas of Cabañas and Chalatenango, among other places.

The lack of a discussion until 2017 of any of the aforementioned legislation drafts in the conservative and elite-dominated Legislative Assembly likely stemmed from a divergence of views even within the FMLN about the shape mining policy should take⁹⁹ as well as the caution with which the FMLN-led government was proceeding until the ICSID litigation was resolved.¹⁰⁰ Yet, notwithstanding the disregard of the legislation drafts by the FMLN government and the Legislative Assembly, Mesa Nacional members found these drafts a useful means of engaging in public debates about policy and

regulation, and remoralising them. In the drafts, they prioritised the state's constitutional obligation to look after the health of citizens and the conservation and protection of the environment, which has a direct bearing on citizens' health: 'the health of the inhabitants of the Republic constitutes a public good' and it is the duty of 'the State to control environmental conditions that may affect [their] health and well-being'.¹⁰¹ Sustainable development, they asserted, can only be carried out by protecting citizens' health and the environment, as well as responsibly managing natural resources. Indeed, they justify both the 2006 and 2013 drafts with the following recital: 'In accordance with Art. 117 of the Constitution, it is the duty of the State to protect natural resources, as well as the diversity and integrity of the environment to guarantee *sustainable development*'.

I suggest that, in contrast to the ICSID proceedings, which they considered exclusionary and whose process was largely shaped by observation of the law, Mesa Nacional members conceived of their creative and experimental engagement with national legislation as a 'field of possibility' that allowed them to imbue debates with different moral values while shaping law. Rather than conducting a wholesale critique of legal formalism, this organisation's members were proactive in engaging and replicating formalist legal instruments and even turned into lawmakers in order to assert their right to shape the public policy that affects them and imbue it with an ethics of care that, as I have argued elsewhere, is largely suffused with Catholic morality. This is the case in El Salvador given the prominence of the country's Catholic Church authorities and the widespread dissemination among mobilised citizens of the key eco-theological ideas contained in Pope Francis's encyclical *Laudato Si'*.¹⁰² Yet Catholic morality in these countries has deeper roots that go back to the 1970s, when liberation theology deeply influenced areas of Central America by promoting political agency, solidary values and social justice underpinned by forms of rights-based citizenship among the poor and disenfranchised.¹⁰³ Yet the influence of environmentalism through the support and funding of international NGOs should not be underestimated.

Mesa Nacional members' engagement of formalist legal arenas through lawmaking suggests that despite the lack of success they experienced for years, they remained convinced that these arenas held a strong sense of promise and would be instrumental in placing care for the environment high on the national agenda. This sense of promise, I argue, was not underpinned as much by a 'fetishization of the law' whereby the law acts as the measure of ethics¹⁰⁴ as by the pragmatic view that legal arenas provide a forum in which to influence the political agenda, which was made manifest by the fact that Mesa Nacional's political-legal action shaped electoral politics, contributed to the enforcement of a *de facto* moratorium and eventually led to a ban. As Sieder has suggested for the case of indigenous communities opposing extraction in Guatemala, 'mimicking and appropriating formal legal instruments and institutions' – through law drafting in the case of El Salvador – can 'challenge and legitimate law with potentially far-reaching consequences for counterhegemonic organization'.¹⁰⁵ This is the case, I argue, because of the potential that citizen lawmaking carries to imbue law with alternative values, such as protection, conservation, and care for both humanity and the environment, thereby moving on from a conception of nature as mere 'resource'.

In February 2017 – after the Catholic Church publicly demonstrated its support of a new legislative initiative to ban mining, and mounting societal pressure ensued – political

parties of all persuasions no longer dared ignore the issue of mining and the impacts thereof. A month later, the mining ban was passed. Aside from a few amendments, the legal text had been shaped by citizen participants in religious organisations and had been modelled on previous citizen legislation drafts; this time the legal aesthetics and jargon were provided by university law professors from El Salvador's Jesuit university. The maintenance of the *de facto* moratorium in El Salvador since 2007 and until mining was definitively banned confirmed and even expanded the sense of promise heralded by the legal, which has led Salvadorans to continue pressing legislative initiatives concerning other environmental issues, such as water regulation, and state responsibility for the failure to adequately address and mitigate climate change.

Conclusion: environmental politics and legal citizenship

Salvadorans' legal endeavours constitute counter-hegemonic challenges.¹⁰⁶ As Salvadoran citizens participating in grassroots movements and NGOs became embroiled in a political struggle against the development of the mining sector in their country, they mobilised legal regimes and instruments, educated themselves to the point of becoming legal experts, and innovated legally. Yet, as the article reveals, their participation has represented more than just a bottom-up development of the law and legal regimes. Through their two *amicus curiae* and law-drafting processes, Salvadoran citizens who are members of Mesa Nacional have not only put forth creative forms of politics and legality but also infused legal arenas and regimes with distinctive values and moralities. Such values and moralities promote the conservation, care and protection of the environment, citizen participation and sovereignty, and forms of development that prioritise both human and environmental rights and relations over economic growth and the governance of territory as merely a repository of resources. Although these are ideologies and moral values partly promoted by the international environmental and development organisations that support and fund them, the embedment in territory and the history of peasant and rural populations weigh heavily.

As expounded in this article, the increasing juridification of environmental politics has contributed to shaping legal cultures in which legal formalism holds an important sway. The dispute over the El Dorado mining project in El Salvador involved tribunals like the ICSID, international law firms and the generation and circulation of a range of legal artefacts, such as all the documentation submitted for the ICSID case, including the two citizen-led *amicus curiae*. Other cases throughout the region likewise point to the relevance of courts, whether subnational, national, regional, or international. While many Salvadorans opposed to extraction denounced certain aspects of formalist legal arenas as disempowering – as articulated in the first *amicus curiae* submitted to the ICSID tribunal and through interviews – they also embraced these arenas as a field of possibility and intervention, as evidenced by their involvement in law drafting. This involvement did not necessarily lead to progress in the legal domain, which they did not attain until 2016 and 2017 with the arbitration award favourable to the Salvadoran state and the ban on mining respectively. Yet it did at least extend the scope and political horizons of their claims. In other words, they have regarded law as a field of possibility that enables thinking, acting and dwelling otherwise.

The two *amicus curiae* delivered by Mesa Nacional to the arbitrating tribunal in the *Pac Rim v. Republic of El Salvador* dispute include explanations that differ dramatically from those of the company and the state. Rather than approaching the dispute as a breach of law, the *amicus curiae* presented it as rooted in politics, and alternative moral values I would add. Mesa Nacional members even questioned whether the tribunal was the appropriate jurisdiction for a political dispute, on the grounds that the ICSID had automatically ruled out Salvadoran citizens as a legitimate disputing party. What is more, both the *amicus curiae* and law drafts evoked a notion of development that contrasted sharply with that upheld by the corporation and arbitrating tribunal. Unlike a form of development led by foreign private investment as a key driving force, Mesa Nacional proposed more participatory approaches that would build upon the lived experiences of political organising of many Salvadorans since the 1960s and 1970s and prioritised local livelihoods and ways of living. Local populations – Mesa Nacional members asserted building upon Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration – must have a say in extractive and other industrial projects that can potentially impact their everyday lives, livelihoods, and habitats.

As I argue elsewhere, Mesa Nacional's understanding of development is also underpinned by an ethics of care towards nature, largely informed by the environmental discourse of international NGOs and the Catholic Church's recent ecological positioning vis-à-vis climate change and environmental degradation – a position that emphasizes the interrelation of the current environmental crisis and global inequality and the need to address them in tandem.¹⁰⁷ The role of Salvadoran citizens and grassroots organisations in lawmaking has thus evinced alternative moralities vis-à-vis development, natural materials, and the territories in which these are deposited. Acquired partly through worlding and inhabiting, as well as mobilised through regional networks, these moralities contrast with the objectification of nature as an exploitable resource that has become so prevalent in modernist understandings of development and legal positivist approaches.¹⁰⁸ The governance and management of natural areas and territory has indeed led us to '[quantify] the unquantifiable' and to become 'cut off from the sensuous world'.¹⁰⁹ Inhabiting those areas, on the other hand, offers the opportunity to build 'another relationship to the world', one 'made up of spaces that are irreducible to each other'.¹¹⁰

Mesa Nacional members have introduced discursive notions of participatory politics and an ethics of care into legal arenas that concern the environment and, in so doing, proposed alternative forms of valuation of the territories that many of the coalition's members inhabit. This is the case even as they retain a human-centred perspective in their experience of a mutual relationship with the environment. Citizen engagements with law thus have a potential to foster nonmarket forms of value vis-à-vis nature, and prioritise principles of interdependency and popular sovereignty, which contrast with top-down, extraction-centred forms of development. In this sense, citizen lawmaking may be considered 'a key mode of contemporary world-making'¹¹¹ – one that through citizen experimentation and innovation can introduce and foster perspectives and even worlds embedded in the territories.¹¹² This form of lawmaking does not necessarily translate into legal successes, and even when it does, it may be undermined by governments. Yet it opens up alternative pathways and introduces other forms of moral and legal reasoning that can enter into dialogue and competition with hegemonic notions in Euro-Western liberal legality.

Notes

1. The only other two countries to have introduced partial mining bans are Costa Rica and Argentina. For further details, see Ainhoa Montoya, 'Post-Extractive Juridification: Undoing the Legal Foundations of Mining in El Salvador', *Geoforum* 138 (2023).
2. John L. Comaroff and Jean Comaroff, 'Law and Disorder in the Postcolony: An Introduction', in *Law and Disorder in the Postcolony*, ed. Jean Comaroff and John L. Comaroff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2006), 26.
3. Julia Eckert et al., 'Introduction: Law's Travels and Transformations', in *Law Against the State: Ethnographic Forays into Law's Transformations*, ed. Julia Eckert et al. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), 15.
4. See Suzana Sawyer, 'Disabling Corporate Sovereignty in a Transnational Lawsuit', *PoLAR: Political and Legal Anthropology Review* 29, no. 1 (2006): 23–43; David Szablowski, *Transnational Law and Local Struggles: Mining, Communities and the World Bank* (Portland: Hart Publishing, 2007); Rachel Sieder, 'Legal Cultures in the (Un)Rule of Law: Indigenous Rights and Juridification in Guatemala', in *Cultures of Legality: Judicialization and Political Activism in Latin America*, ed. Javier Couso, Alex Huneeus, and Rachel Sieder (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 161–81.
5. Alexandra Huneeus, Javier Couso, and Rachel Sieder, 'Cultures of Legality: Judicialization and Political Activism in Contemporary Latin America', in *Cultures of Legality: Judicialization and Political Activism in Latin America*, ed. Javier Couso, Alexandra Huneeus, and Rachel Sieder (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 6.
6. The main repository employed for the research is *The Legal Cultures of the Subsoil*, both a research output and a basic research infrastructure for this article's legal document analysis. The Legal Cultures of the Subsoil is a digital, open access database containing information and key legal documents and reports on paradigmatic conflicts over mining in Central America and Mexico. <https://doi.org/10.14296/SLWU8713>
7. John Ferejohn, 'Judicializing Politics, Politicizing Law', *Law and Contemporary Problems* 65, no. 3 (2002): 41–68; Comaroff and Comaroff, 'Law and Disorder in the Postcolony'; Ran Hirschl, 'The Judicialization of Politics', in *The Oxford Handbook of Political Science*, ed. Robert Goodin (Oxford Academic, 2013).
8. See Jean Comaroff and John L. Comaroff, *Law and Disorder in the Postcolony* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2006).
9. Pilar Domingo, 'Judicialization of Politics or Politicization of the Judiciary? Recent Trends in Latin America', *Democratization* 11, no. 1 (2004): 104–26; Rachel Sieder, Line Schjolden, and Alan Angell, eds., *The Judicialization of Politics in Latin America* (New York and Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2005); Javier Couso, Alex Huneeus, and Rachel Sieder, eds., *Cultures of Legality: Judicialization and Political Activism in Latin America* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010).
10. Huneeus, Couso, and Sieder, 'Cultures of Legality', 9.
11. Yanna Yannakakis, 'Indigenous People and Legal Culture in Spanish America', *History Compass* 11, no. 11 (2013): 931–47; Keebet Von Benda-Beckmann and Bertram Turner, 'Anthropological Roots of Global Legal Pluralism', in *The Oxford Handbook of Global Legal Pluralism*, ed. Paul Schiff Berman (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020), 67–142.
12. See Huneeus, Couso, and Sieder, 'Cultures of Legality', 5; Rachel Sieder, "'Indigenous Peoples' Rights and the Law in Latin America", in *Handbook of Indigenous Peoples' Rights*, ed. Corinne Lennox and Damien Short (New York: Routledge, 2015), 414–23.
13. Terence Turner, 'Human Rights, Human Difference: Anthropology's Contribution to an Emancipatory Cultural Politics', *Journal of Anthropological Research* 53, no. 3 (1997): 280–82.
14. Mark Goodale, 'Human Rights After the Post-Cold War', in *Human Rights at the Crossroads*, ed. Mark Goodale (Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press, 2013), 5–6. See also Jane K. Cowan, Marie Bénédicte Dembour and Richard A. Wilson, 'Introduction', in *Culture and Rights: Anthropological Perspectives*, ed. Jane K. Cowan, Marie Bénédicte

- Dembour and Richard A. Wilson (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001), 1, 8; Eckert et al., 'Introduction: Law's Travels and Transformations', 2.
15. Comaroff and Comaroff, 'Law and Disorder in the Postcolony', 32–33.
 16. Mark Goodale, *Anthropology and Law: A Critical Introduction* (New York: New York University Press, 2017), 3.
 17. See Greg Grandin, *The Last Colonial Massacre: Latin America in the Cold War* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2004).
 18. Julia Eckert, Brian Donahoe, Christian Strümpell, and Zerrim Özlem Biner, eds., *Law against the State: Ethnographic Forays into Law's Transformations* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), 2.
 19. Boaventura de Sousa Santos, *Towards a New Legal Common Sense: Law, Globalization and Emancipation* (London: Butterworths LexisNexis, 2002), 437.
 20. Huneeus, Couso, and Sieder, 'Cultures of Legality', 11; Rachel Sieder, 'The Juridification of Politics', in *The Oxford Handbook of Law and Anthropology*, ed. Marie-Claire Foblets et al. (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020), 1–17.
 21. See Sally Engle Merry, 'Transnational Human Rights and Local Activism: Mapping the Middle', *American Anthropologist* 108, no. 1 (2006): 38–51.
 22. Von Benda-Beckmann and Turner, 'Anthropological Roots of Global Legal Pluralism'.
 23. *Ibid.*
 24. Guillermo O'Donnell, 'Afterword', in *The Judicialization of Politics in Latin America*, ed. Rachel Sieder, Line Schjolden, and Alan Angell (New York and Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2005), 293.
 25. Günther Teubner, 'Juridification: Concepts, Aspects, Limits, Solutions', in *Juridification of Social Spheres: A Comparative Analysis in the Areas of Labor, Corporate, Antitrust and Social Welfare Law*, ed. Günther Teubner (Berlin and New York: Walter de Gruyter, 1987), 3–48.
 26. Daniel Loick, 'Juridification', in *The Cambridge Habermas Lexicon*, ed. Amy Allen and Eduardo Mendieta (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 208.
 27. Goodale, *Anthropology and Law*, 4; see also Ainhoa Montoya, 'On Care for Our Common Home: Ecological Materiality and Sovereignty over the Lempa Transboundary Watershed', *Journal of Latin American Studies* 53, no. 2 (2021): 297–322.
 28. Teubner, 'Juridification: Concepts, Aspects, Limits, Solutions', 389; Loick, 'Juridification', 209.
 29. Cited in Cowan, Dembour and Wilson, 'Introduction', 13.
 30. Lars Chr. Blichner and Anders Molander, 'Mapping Juridification', *European Law Journal* 14, no. 1 (2008): 36–54; Eckert et al., 'Introduction: Law's Travels and Transformations'; Sieder, 'The Juridification of Politics', 1–17.
 31. Huneeus, Couso, and Sieder, 'Cultures of Legality'.
 32. Eckert et al., 'Introduction: Law's Travels and Transformations', 12.
 33. Goodale, *Anthropology and Law*, 23, 108.
 34. Eckert et al., *Law Against the State*, 3.
 35. Boaventura de Sousa Santos and César Rodríguez-Garavito, 'Law, Politics, and the Subaltern in Counter-Hegemonic Globalization', in *Law and Globalization from Below: Towards a Cosmopolitan Legality*, ed. César Rodríguez-Garavito and Boaventura de Sousa Santos (Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 12.
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69. Over the course of the proceedings, the company raised this amount to US \$315 million.
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71. Group interview with MINEC government officials, conducted on 17 February 2014, San Salvador, El Salvador.
72. Dewey & LeBoeuf was discontinued in May 2012 and the team of four lawyers working on the case moved to Foley Hoag.
73. Specifically, the Salvadoran defense argued that Pac Rim failed to provide (a) proof of land ownership or authorisation to use the land where the mining project was located and (b) a feasibility study – both requirements for applications for exploitation concessions according to the 1996 Mining Law (Art. 37). In addition, the Salvadoran defense asserted that the company never satisfied MARN's requirements for an environmental permit.
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75. Interview with Elsy, ADES and Mesa Nacional member, conducted on 14 February 2014, Guacotecti, Cabañas Department, El Salvador.
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Ethics statement

This research has received approval from the University of London Research Ethics Committee.

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